

FIRST REPORT

PERIOD: 30 Sep 2019 - 29 Mar 2020

PROJECT: CONSTRUCTION OF FOUR UNITS OF SQUAT TOILETS AT LEA TAKUSHARA & LEA KUNYAMI COMMUNITY SCHOOLS / DRILLING OF BOREHOLE & INSTALLATION OF HANDPUMPS AT EACH SCHOOL AND PRINTING / DISTRIBUTION OF EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS ON BASIC HYGIENE AT EACH SCHOOL

TASKS COMPLETED.

Geological Surveys have been conducted in the two community elementary schools; LEA Takushara and LEA Kunyami to ascertain the water levels before drilling the boreholes.

Technical and Building design for the squat toilets have been completed.

TASKS IN PROGRESS.

Analyzing the results of the geological surveys which ascertain what works best for each depth in both schools: This analysis is being carried out by the drilling engineers and a conclusion is yet to be reached.

Designing hygiene promotion, information, education and communication materials for elementary school pupils.

Wellbee says

be well be clean,
Wash your
hands!

BARRIERS/DELAYS

A major delay experienced was in cash advancement for the project. The organization got advanced February 2020 for a project that was awarded September 2019- 5 months after.

Another delay we have experienced is the lock down as a result of the Corona Virus pandemic.

NEXT STEPS

The drilling machines will go in to the schools as soon as the lock down or quarantine is over / at any available chance or at any willingness shown by the drilling company to go to work.

CONCLUSION

The project is expected to be completed in the coming months and meeting its targeted time of completion of September 2020.